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THE LEARNING ANALYTICS ADOPTION IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES OF PAKISTAN: BARRIERS AND RESPONSES BY LIBRARIANS

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Abstract

Learning analytics (LA) is rising as new area of research and application. Higher education institutions are increasingly benefiting from learning analytics implementation. Therefore, present study designed with aim to highlight the potential impediments and training needs for deploying LA in academic libraries of Pakistan. This study opted quantitative research based on survey approach, 211 library professionals of higher education institutions have participated in the study. Findings unveiled strong correlation among all challenges, and training needs for learning analytics adoption. Moreover, our study identified probable challenges and areas of training needs, which are considered as crucial prior to implement LA in academic libraries. Outcomes of this study serve as reference, and important practical implications for university high ups, policymakers, and library professionals for successfully implementation of learning analytics.

Keywords: Academic Libraries, Adoption, Learning Analytics, Libraries, Pakistan

Introduction

The massive increase in data related to learning, which is generated within digital learning environment. Analyzing such massive data through various tools, and methodologies of learning analytics can yield detailed insights into student learning processes, and outcomes. Therefore, employing learning analytics approaches is regarded as an auspicious way, to improving assessment practices (Raković et al., 2023). Learning analytics employs massive data that relate to learners' interactions in online learning, to comprehend and improve learning (Gašević et al., 2022). Thus, learning analytics is considered as an approach of tracking and analyzing data that relate to students' online learning activities, the core of learning analytics in online education is to improve the learning expertise, and entire educational progress (Quadri et al., 2021). The following is the much acknowledged and widely cited definition of learning analytics is "the measurement, collection, analysis, and reporting of data about learners and their contexts, for purposes of understanding and optimizing learning and the environments in which it occurs" (LAK '11: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Learning Analytics and Knowledge, 2011). Learning analytics has been significantly recognized for its potential, to enhance competencies associated with subject development, as it enables students to reflect on their learning processes, and advancement of skills, thereby raising self-awareness of their talents and shortcomings. In addition, it is believed that learning analytics fosters goal orientation, metacognitive skills, and the ability to learn effectively (Kleimola & Leppisaari, 2022). Higher education institutions are progressively adopting the learning analytics, for recognizing and interceding students those are at the risk of poor performance, and potential dropout (Larrabee Sønderlund et al., 2019). Despite the rising significance of data-driven decision-making in university libraries, there is scarceness of research on data analytics. Thus, LA help libraries in data-driven decision making (Roy, 2025).

Furthermore, complying recent trends, the higher education is insisting on quantitative analytical methods for assessing educational attainments. Similarly, the academic libraries are continuously endeavoring to measure their effectiveness on learners' attainment and retention through learning analytics methods (Robertshaw et al., 2019). Further, the librarians have always supported the mission of academic institutions, through participation in pursuing learning assessment, research, advancing accreditation endeavors, and collaboration with faculty (Blummer et al., 2018). In addition to this, academic

libraries are actively engaging in collecting and evaluating student data, this shift comes under the realm of learning analytics, in this endeavor library professionals face some issues that relates to ethics and privacy (Jones & Hinchliffe, 2023). In addition to this, there is inadequacy of literature concerning the challenges on LA (Gašević et al., 2022).

Therefore, presence of multifarious challenges, which may cause as impediment in adoption of learning analytics, these are discussed in subsequent section. The current study designed with aim to outline the challenges to implement LA, and analyze their relationship. The outcomes of this research will be helpful and efficacious for higher education institutions, and their libraries to successfully adopt LA.

Research Questions

1. What are prospect challenges to adopt LA in academic libraries of Pakistan?
2. What is relationship among these challenges for adoption of LA in academic libraries of Pakistan?
3. What are the training needs of library professionals, to implement LA in academic libraries of Pakistan?

Review of the Literature

Challenges to Implement Learning Analytics

Insufficiency of prowess, in technology and pedagogy, impedes to integrate LA (Kaliisa et al., 2021). Therefore, Implementation of LA demand's institutions, up skilling, expanding resources. There are Myriad of challenges, those are, Insufficient funds, dearth of infrastructure, data incompetence, inexpert personnel, organization's culture, and ethics and privacy (Gašević & Dawson, 2019). Moreover, according to Tsai & Gasevic, (2017) Scarceness of competencies in higher management, to put into practice and monitor LA in an effective manner. Ignorance of stakeholders' participation to implement LA. Insufficiency of pedagogical techniques to eliminate learning difficulties, pointed through analytics. Scantiness of trainings for empowering users to apply LA. Further, scarcity of data-driven substantiation, about influence of analytics provoke the interventions. In order to handle concerns related to ethics & privacy, there is scarceness of policies that are particularly customized for LA. Further, Sousa et al., (2021) highlighted that, LA deal with distinctive issues, technical issues are Heterogeneity of data. Therefore, it becomes very difficult to manage and interpret distinctive forms of data from diverse sources. Quality of data, to discern understandable data from huge data, and there is heterogeneity in tools, approaches for data processing, and there is need for efficacious visualization, so that users can easily analyze information. Moreover, data quality and privacy are among the core challenges, in addition, the technical troubles highlighted as limited internet and insufficiency of devices. Although, at higher education level, little participation of stockholders, concerns associated with data governance, information assurance and ethics.

Furthermore, there are also pedagogical issues, such as: Participation of teachers and students in LA, to verify LA influence on education, to document students' behavioral trends, Pedagogical analysis of information, produced subsequent to analysis of data (Guenaga & Garaizar, 2016). In addition to this, Ferguson & Hall, (2012) stated that dealing with diverse datasets, incorporating familiarity with learning sciences, devising comprehensive ethical framework are the among challenges. Valenzuela et al., (2021) explored that the Ignorance of respecting informed consent and users' privacy are among

the issues. In addition, protecting users' information is problematic task. Moreover, the profusion of learning data is challenging, because massive data requires specialize analytical tools and expertise, to get purposeful results efficiently (Chatti et al., 2014). Owing to profusion of data, the data-tracing, gathering, and assessing relevant data are the prospect challenges. Further, deficiency of association to learning sciences, and issues pertains to data-ethics and privacy (Avella et al., 2016). Substantial part of LA research and practice, depends on data digitally generated and gathered in information system, which is constantly hard to provide accurate, and swift interpretation of elements that influence on learning (Cukurova et al., 2020a). Data accumulation, tracking, comprehension, and preciseness of data are among the challenges. Moreover, to handle big data issues, specialize technical infrastructure is needed, which efficiently provide real time feedback. In addition, there is dearth of comprehensive literature on impact of LA on teaching in HEI-setting, and most of LA systems designed without consulting the stockholders i.e. "students and teachers". Further challenges are, Lack of human factor toward change adaptability, privacy & transparency in using data, insufficiency of relevant skills and analytical expertise, finite comprehending about aggregated data (El Alfy et al., 2019). Information deficit, possible violation of students' privacy and incomprehension of data by tutors (Paolucci et al., 2024a). In pursuit of deploying Innovative technology and services, libraries confront numerous challenges, such as: privacy, financial limitations, insufficient infrastructure, and scantiness staff training (Hamad et al., 2023). Similarly, in context of libraries, the presence of insufficient infrastructure, need for training in specific areas, staff inexperience, outlined as main challenges (Nosheen, 2025).

Learning Analytics Training for Librarians

According to, Isibika et al., (2021) the training keeps conversant with new trends, innovations in the field, provide boost to working capability and services. Moreover, assessing training needs is crucial, to identify and remedying the skills and knowledge inadequacies among staff members (Muneja et al., 2024). Moreover, to ascertain the training and information needs of staff, the focused assessment essential for organizations, to look into shortcomings of staff knowledge and expertise (Purnell, 2020). The considerable need for training and persistent support by organization is pivotal, to effectually manage, gaining stakeholders' comprehension, and objectives associated with learning analytics (Gray et al., 2022).

Methods of the Study

This investigation employed a descriptive measurement approach; therefore, the survey was carried out to accumulate the data, through a questionnaire with "five-point Likert scale". This study included 211 library professionals from higher education institutions of Pakistan. Questionnaire's Pretest helps to avoid inaccuracy in survey questions; therefore, pretesting is better to eliminate such fallaciousness from research instrument. In addition, the pilot testing is also helpful to point out possible issues across entire survey (Ruel et al., 2016). Therefore, for the "Pretest & Pilot testing" Twenty-three 23 questionnaires were sent to librarians, who possess higher qualification (i.e. M.Phil or Ph.D), and have research experience. After incorporating some minor changes to the tool. A link to online questionnaire sent on email address of librarians, in total, 211 completed questionnaires received. The data analysis was performed by employing Pearson correlation through

“Statistical Package for Social Sciences” SPSS-20. Because, correlation relates to the association among different variables (Kronthaler, 2023), the correlation and regression analysis are much employed common statistical techniques, which are used to ascertain the link among quantitative variables (Aslam & Imdad Ullah, 2023). The technique we applied is also performed in by Ahmad et al., (2019) and Fan et al., (2014)

Results of the Study

In total, 211 library professionals from Pakistan’s higher education institutions, participated in this study, the table 1 depicts the characteristics of respondents, which were categorized in their gender (128 male, 60.7%) and (83 females, 39.3%), and their qualification was 147 BS-LIS, (69.7%), 55 M.Phil. (26.1%), and 09 Ph.D. (4.2%), and the experience of librarians was categorized as 86 (40.8) librarians have up to 10 years’ experience, 54 (25.6) library professionals described to have 11-15 experience in years, 47 (22.3%) librarians hold the experience from 16 to 20 years, whereas only 24 (11.3%) librarians, gained 21-25 years’ experience, participated in this investigation.

Table-1: *Characteristics of Participants*

Category	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	128	60.7
	Female	83	39.3
Qualification	BS (LIS)	147	69.7
	M.PHIL	55	26.1
	PhD	9	4.2
Experience (In Years)	1-10	86	40.8
	11-15	54	25.6
	16-20	47	22.3
	21-25	24	11.3

The Provisions of Learning Analytics for the Implementation process in Libraries

The outcomes in Table 2 highlight significant correlation among all variables, which are related to the training needs of participants, for the adoption of Learning Analytics (LA) in academic libraries. Hence, these outcomes substantiate that librarians are the well informed about the importance of various areas of training and required skills for successfully deploying “learning analytics” in their libraries. Moreover, Figure 1, represent the scatter plot matrix, which is pointing a substantial correlation among all the variables.

Table 2: *Correlation of Training Needs of Library Professionals*

1. Analytics & Data visualization	2. Computer hardware.	3. Software applications	4. Data protection	5. Data privacy & ethical use	6. CPD
2. .776** .000					
3. .785** .000	.791** .000				
4. .613** .000	.545** .000	.678** .000			
5. .522** .000	.501** .000	.637** .000	.724** .000		

6.	.565**	.496**	.598**	.721**	.778**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Figure 1: Training Needs of Library Professionals

Table 3: *Barriers For The Implementation Of Learning Analytics*

Correlations	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. LA awareness											
2. Data privacy policies	.729**										
3. Infrastructure	.612**	.569**									
4. Data protection	.578**	.582**	.736**								
5. Data visualization	.595**	.563**	.495**	.537**							
6. Hardware expertise	.528**	.524**	.593**	.655**	.756**						
7. Data storage facilities	.505**	.446**	.642**	.673**	.617**	.788**					
8. Software expertise	.469**	.428**	.610**	.608**	.505**	.671**	.728**				
9. Limited budget	.505**	.495**	.612**	.595**	.565**	.598**	.686**	.684**			
10. Staff capabilities	.475**	.464**	.546**	.676**	.593**	.655**	.710**	.685**	.690**		
11. Limited research	.481**	.472**	.599**	.686**	.542**	.607**	.711**	.663**	.660**	.767**	
12. Higher management	.509**	.462**	.551**	.649**	.543**	.561**	.623**	.570**	.547**	.650**	.705**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Considering the cited literature, this study outlined the 12 challenges, which are deemed as main impediments in deploying LA in academic libraries.

Table 3, details the presence of remarkable correlation among entire 12 variables, which pertain to the challenges, for the adoption LA in academic libraries. Therefore, these outcomes substantiate that dearth of LA awareness is correlated to Inadequacy of privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management.

Absence of policies related to data privacy is correlated with dearth of LA awareness, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management.

Infrastructure insufficiency is correlated to dearth of LA awareness, privacy policies, data

protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management.

Data protection facilities' paucity interrelated with dearth of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management. Data visualization skills' insufficiency associated with dearth of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, Data protection facilities, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management.

Hardware expertise scantiness is related with scarcity of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, software expertise, data storage, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management. Data storage facilities' shortage is linked with Inadequacy of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management.

Software expertise' limitedness is interrelated with Inadequacy of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise hardware, data storage, limited budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management. Limited budget is linked with Inadequacy of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, , staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management

Staff capabilities' dearth is correlated with Inadequacy of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, limited budget, limited research, and higher management

Limited research is correlated with all outlined challenges.

Higher management perform an essential role to attain LA adoption. A clear association outlined among higher management and all variables. Inadequacy of LA awareness, privacy policies, infrastructure, data protection & visualization, expertise in hardware and software, data storage, limited budget, staff capabilities, limited research, and higher management. Furthermore, our outcomes are linked to (Kaliisa et al., 2021) that Insufficiency of prowess, in technology and pedagogy, impedes to integrate LA. In addition to this, the scarcity of ethics and privacy, absence of analytical capabilities, and dearth of technological resources & capacity are the main among challenges to deploy LA (Klein et al., 2019; Shannan et al., 2023). Figure 2, depicts a scatter plot matrix of correlations based upon Table 3, which denotes a remarkable link among all the variables relate to challenges. Therefore, Implementation of LA demand's institutions, up skilling staff's expertise and expanding resources. Thus, outcomes revealed that all variables, related to challenges are core and interrelated. Therefore, it is necessary to consider these challenges, prior to implement LA.

Figure-2: Challenges

Discussion

The area of “learning analytics” is now viewed amongst the emerging disciplines, which present multiple challenges and training needs of professionals, particularly concerning its implementation. In preparation for LA implementation, institutions should evaluate probable benefits and challenges of LA (Morales-menendez et al., 2022). A remarkable aspect of this examination is that it probed the challenges and training needs, which are regarded as core, to successful deploying learning analytics in context of academic libraries, in Pakistan. Thus, our study imparts new sagacity regarding Smooth and efficaciously implementation of LA.

(Morales-menendez et al., 2022)(Morales-menendez et al., 2022)(Morales-menendez et al., 2022)(Morales-menendez et al., 2022)(Morales-menendez et al., 2022)Concerning the

training needs and their correlation, this study highlighted 6 core elements, 1. Analytics & Data visualization 2. Computer hardware. 3. Software applications 4. Data protection 5. Data privacy & ethical use 6. CPD, these elements relate to the training needs library professionals. Moreover, the strong correlation observed in table 3, among all 6 variables that pertains to training needs of library professional. Training aids to accelerate technology adoption by offering the necessary framework for individuals, to learn new technologies effectively (Jarvie-eggart et al., 2024). In addition, the essential aspect of continuing professional development (CPD) is keeping personnel well-informed and applicable at their workplace (Goulding & Campbell-Meier, 2025), and CPD keeps associated with profession (Moonasar, 2024). Library and LA experts have suggested that, the training, collaboration, teamwork and support from higher management are among the crucial factors, for the successful deployment of LA in libraries (Sant-geronikolou et al., 2019).

In the perspective of the challenges, this investigation unveiled the 12 challenges, which pertains to adoption of LA in academic libraries' context. Further, we assessed the relationship among these 12 variables concerning the challenges, strong correlation among all variables revealed. Our results are parallel with the various studies, regarding the dearth of ethics and data privacy policies (Paolucci et al., 2024; Avella et al., 2016), limited budget, insufficiency of infrastructure (hardware & software), personnel inexperience, insufficiency of trainings (Nosheen, 2025; Hamad et al., 2023) scantiness of higher management's competencies and interest and data visualization skills (El Alfy et al., 2019; Gaševi & Dawson, 2019) and limited research in LA domain (Cukurova et al., 2020b). Therefore, these outcomes indicate that the library staff working in those libraries are well informed about deploying LA, and they consider that these challenges restrain in smooth adopting and service delivery of LA, in their libraries. Therefore, it is crucial to assess and eliminate these berries, prior to integrate or initiate any LA-tools or service. Further, HEI should focus on ameliorating in these highlighted areas such as: improving infrastructure in terms of technological tools (hardware & applications), data security, designing institution's privacy policies, and grants. Therefore, on the basis of these out comes, it is very necessary for the institutions to keep their concentration on these area training needs, and design a training policy and mechanism for their staff in those required area of training, to implement and service delivery of LA. Further, there is a need to continue revision of LIS curriculum, and hands-on practices in accordance with latest tech-trends and rapid transformations within society.

Study Limitation

One of the limiting factors of this probe is that descriptive data accumulated from only library professionals. However, we should also gather data from institutions' higher management, whose opinion and feedback could yield more insight on this topic.

Conclusion

This study unveiled the challenges and required areas of training for academic library workers, these elements viewed as inevitable, to facilitate LA implementation in academic libraries. In addition, this work showed that librarians are eager and cognizant about LA deployment in their libraries, and outputs from our study provide a base and necessary guideline for upper management of higher education institutions, and library managers in

decision-making within university libraries for productive adoption of LA. Thus, this investigation contributes to the library literature by suggesting a new direction for the application of learning analytics in the academic libraries. The findings support the notion that, although there is scope for the improvement library services and introducing new services such as learning analytics, which positively influence the students.

In future research, there is a need for in-depth investigation through "mixed methods research", by participation of all stockholders i.e. (institutional higher-seat management, senior library professionals, faculty, and students) to study comprehensively and framing policy & standards for LA integration at national level. By this way, we will further expand the literature through examining the usage of learning analytics in all types of libraries. Further, investigating on that area, which impact the operationalization of learning analytics in libraries, including legal and policy considerations, privacy concerns, and data ownership issues. A comprehensive examination of these elements will yield better, exact and detailed conclusions.

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